

Digital Transformation in Smart Cities: Decentralized Architecture for Sustainable Development within the Web 3.0 Ecosystem

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Abstract

In the burgeoning landscape of smart city infrastructure, the proliferation of Web 3.0 systems introduces distinct challenges, particularly concerning data security and scalability. The evolution of Industry 4.0 and Society 5.0 marks a significant progression in urban system capabilities. Central to this progression is the harmonious fusion of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) with the latest technological innovations, covering the broad spectrum of production and enterprise activities. This fusion is pivotal in stimulating an active flow of information, cultivating trust, improving operational efficiency, and elevating profitability for a wide array of stakeholders. This study investigates the congruence between the ReFi (Regenerative Finance) concept, which is founded on eight essential principles, and the principles underlying Smart City initiatives, both of which advocate for sustainable urban progression. The ReFi concept's principles are also integral to the Smart City framework. The anticipated scenario includes the formulation of smart contracts and their implementation on a blockchain network, which will manage access roles in IoT data sensing. The research's objective is to survey and suggest a framework and key considerations for the design and execution of the Web 3.0 ecosystem. This ecosystem represents the amalgamation of progress in the Internet-of-Things (IoT), Artificial Intelligence (AI), ReFi, Decentralized Finance (DeFi), and smart cities. The study emphasizes the revolutionary capacity of Web 3.0 to drive cities into a future that is not only more intelligent but also more robust, flexible, and responsive to the ever-changing demands of society.

Keywords: Natural capitalism, Sustainability, Smart city, Web 3.0

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1. Introduction

Natural capitalism adopts the stance that there is nothing fundamentally flawed about the existing system and that whatever flaws do exist will have technical fixes—as in smart city solutions for perceived urban problems. This assumption does not factor in that market economics have no moral compass, as promoted in Milton Friedman’s dictum “Greed is Good.” The amoral imperative that the ownership of the entire planet remains, and should continue to remain in private hands “a monistic distortion (by which everything is considered capital is introduced and the reciprocal independence among factors of production as sources of value is eliminated” [7].

What is Society 5.0. In particular, the focus is on the following key concepts which are parallel aspects of the society: “a human-centered society,” “merging cyberspace with physical space,” “a knowledge-intensive society,” and “a data-driven society.” Understanding these four concepts enables us to develop the approach required to make Society 5.0 a reality [5].

Understanding economies as a network of interdependent agents bound in a common cause of social, environmental, and economic wellbeing. This change in thinking implies embracing circular value-chains, which primarily focus on lasting constructive practice rather than on short-term monetary gains. From ‘how much money’ to ‘where the money goes’ to create lasting holistically, beneficial impacts can thus become the new mantra [5].

Development of new strategies for favoring the transition to smart cities, integrating existing urban plans and redefine them in a common and unique sustainable urban plan (mobility, energy, ICT...), that would implement a holistic strategy with the objective to transform the city and to make it smarter [10].

2. Review

The idea of smart city has caught the attention of almost all countries in the world, including China. So far, more than 1000 smart cities have been initiated or constructed around the world, especially in Europe, North America, and Asia. The Chinese government has made great efforts in smart city construction in the past decades. In 2009, the Chinese government put forward the construction of smart cities. The Ministry of Housing and Urban-Rural Development officially published the first batch of pilot lists of smart cities in 2012, including 90 prefectures and county-level cities [6].

Figure 1. Smart city [8].

Figure 1. shows the smart city conceptual framework derived from Yagitcanlar (Yigitcanlar et al., 2019a) [8].

In fact, study results showed that citizens preferred smart city projects as a means of improving their quality of life and boosting convenience through the enhancement of urban infrastructures, among other things [9].

	Society 1.0	Society 2.0	Society 3.0	Society 4.0	Society 5.0
Society	Hunter-gatherer	Agrarian	Industrial	Information	Super smart
Productive approach	Capture/Gather	Manufacture	Mechanization	ICT	Merging of cyberspace and physical space
Material	Stone•Soil	Metal	Plastic	Semiconductor	Material 5.0*
Transport	Foot	Ox, horse	Motor car, boat, plane	Multimobility	Autonomous driving
Form of settlement	Nomadic, small settlement 	Fortified city 	Linear (industrial) city 	Network city 	Autonomous decentralized city
City ideals	Viability	Defensiveness	Functionality	Profitability	Humanity

Figure 2. Contextualizing Society 5.0 [5].

Figure 2. shows categories created by the authors. Source: Produced by authors. Research conducted by the University of Tokyo's Material Innovation Research Center [5].

Table 1. Industry 4.0 vs. Society 5.0 [5].

Title	Industrie 4.0 (Germany)	Society 5.0 (Japan)
Design	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •High-Tech Strategy 2020 Action Plan for Germany (BMBF, 2011) •Recommendations for implementing the strategic initiative INDUSTRIE 4.0 (Industrie 4.0 Working Group, 2013) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •5th Science and Technology Basic Plan (released 2016) •Comprehensive Strategy on Science, Technology and Innovation for 2017 (released 2017)
Objectives, scope	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Smart factories • Focuses on manufacturing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Super-smart society • Society as a whole
Key phrases	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Cyber-physical systems (CPS) •Internet of Things (IoT) •Mass customization 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High-level convergence of cyberspace and physical space • Balancing economic development with resolution of social issues • Human-centered society

As shown in Table 1, there is a comparison between industry 4.0 and Society 5.0 based on three dimensions of Design, Objective scope, and Key phrases [5].

2.1. ReFi

As ReFi is a rapidly growing movement, this list is not exhaustive. It is also important to note that these classifications are based on the aims of ReFi projects as described in their public-facing communications, rather than their material outcomes. Some projects listed are still in development and may not achieve their desired outcomes [4].

Tokenized carbon credits are central to Regenerative Finance (ReFi), a subset of Decentralized Finance (DeFi), named after a broader movement in regenerative capitalism, which is primarily concerned with climate change mitigation through digital assets of various kinds. Tokenized carbon credits have been studied in relation to the energy industry, the transition into sustainable energy, and how to maximize the efficiency of current grids by allowing for peer-to-peer energy trading. There is also research regarding solutions for measurement, reporting, and verification (MRV), and sustainable supply chains [1].

List of projects: Carbon market, Incentivizing regenerative practices, Oracle/Climate data, Community/DAO, Community Land Trusts, Network, Game, NFT/Fundraising, Investor, Energy Grid, Renewable Energy/RECs, Infrastructure/blockchain, and Staking/Blockchain offsetting [4].

According to those we interviewed, five key motivations underpin ReFi [4]:

- Redefining value

ReFi aims to connect ecological value with economic value, using blockchain tools to financially incentivize regenerative, climate-positive actions [4].

- Making climate-change action more accessible

ReFi aims to make funding for climate-positive projects more efficient and accessible to communities on the ground [4].

- Data accessibility

ReFi aims to improve transparency and accessibility of climate data by bringing it on-chain [13].

- Solving the global coordination failure

ReFi aims to leverage the immutable ledger of blockchain to support the coordination of diverse actors in climate governance [4].

- Improving carbon markets

ReFi aims to improve the transparency, efficiency, quality and liquidity of carbon markets through blockchain technology [4].

2.2. The Modern Humanity and Capitalism Based upon Things

If we are to rethink what humanity is today, we have to interrogate the relationship between humanity and capitalism, the principle that has significantly regulated the contemporary world. Michel Foucault asked this question around half a century ago in 1966 [5]:

As the archaeology of our thought easily shows, man is an invention of recent date. And one perhaps nearing its end. If those arrangements were to disappear as they appeared, if some event of which we can at the moment do no more than sense the possibility—without knowing either what its form will be or what it promises—were to cause them to crumble, as the ground of Classical thought did, at the end of the eighteenth century, then one can certainly wager that man would be erased, like a face drawn in sand at the edge of the sea. The era of classical thought, which existed through the seventeenth and eighteenth centuries, gave way to the era of modernity. The era of modernity that existed in the nineteenth century was underpinned by the concept of “homme” that is “man” or “humanity.” According to Foucault, this concept would come to an end in the twentieth century [5].

2.2.1. Role of Cash in a Data-Driven Society

Two Ways of Going Cashless

Cash is the most essential infrastructure for underpinning people’s economic activities. IT and the IoT transform cash in two main ways. First, they make cash digital, where once it was physical. The expression “going cashless” usually refers to promoting monetary transactions through credit or debit cards or by other alternatives to handing over hard cash. As used here however, “going cashless” refers to the use of digital currency as an alternative to hard cash. The Bank of Japan (BOJ), which is responsible for issuing the nation’s banknotes, can track the circulation of each 10,000-yen banknote based on its serial numbers. The BOJ cannot, however, tell who currently holds the banknote or what it has been exchanged for and where. In this respect, hard cash has a very anonymous element. This anonymity is one of the defining features of hard cash, but it also represents a technical limitation. With digital currency, on the other hand, you can, at least in principle, trace who has the money and where it is being used. The second kind of cash transformation concerns the proliferation of moneyless transactions. In other words, people are buying things without hard cash or electronic money. When we buy something, we usually pay for it in money. This payment provides a source of revenue to the seller. In this way, money becomes the economic lifeblood [5].

If paying for things with money is “monetary economics,” then paying for things without money is “nonmonetary economics.” Historically, nonmonetary economics prevailed, but monetary economics rapidly proliferated after the Industrial Revolution. Nowadays, we usually measure a country’s economic well-being by the scale of its monetary economy, and disregard its nonmonetary economy. Hence, the nonmonetary economy is considered only minimally when calculating gross domestic product (GDP). The reason is that there is a tacit understanding that nonmonetary economy tends to be smaller relative to the monetary economy. However, this situation has recently started to change. Technological innovation is driving the proliferation of nonmonetary economies. The world is increasingly going cashless. “Going cashless” might not be an ideal term, but it does usually refer to the proliferation of nonmonetary economies. Wikipedia is an example of this trend. It was not so long ago that each family kept large encyclopedias, such as the Encyclopedia Britannica, on their bookshelves. These encyclopedias of course had to be paid for, and they were by no means

cheap. Adults and children alike would look up facts in these encyclopedias. Nowadays, we use Wikipedia instead [5].

In nonmonetary economies, the reverse is true. Because there is no pricing, the producers are unsure at what volume to produce the products. Consequently, the supply can be low even when the demand is high. Another difference is that although monetary economies can be measured using economic metrics such as GDP, these metrics have little use in nonmonetary economies because the activities therein are not calculated in monetary terms. Thus, a new kind of system is necessary to measure the vibrancy of nonmonetary economies. In the following section, we consider the backgrounds to these two forms of cashlessness and their significance. Although WTP and WTA are effective measures of economic impact in theory, it may not be practically feasible to conduct the surveys on a scale sufficiently large enough to gage the overall state of a nonmonetary economy. There instead needs to be a technology that can measure nonmonetary activity granularly and frequently. Hitachi developed a system that uses sensors to measure happiness; something similar to this is needed for nonmonetary economies [5].

2.3. Blockchain and Web 3.0

In the recent years, tokenization of (physical) assets and the creation of a digital version that is stored on the blockchain gained more interest. By utilizing blockchain technology, asset ownership can be tokenized, which enables fractional ownership, reduces intermediaries, and provides a secure and transparent ledger. This not only increases liquidity but also expands access to previously illiquid assets (like carbon offsets). The blockchain ledger allows for real-time settlement of transactions, increasing efficiency and reducing the risk of fraud. Additionally, tokens can be programmed to include certain rules and restrictions, such as limiting the number of tokens that can be issued or specifying how they can be traded, which can provide greater transparency and control over the asset [11].

2.3.1. Impact of AI in Web 3.0 on Various Actors

The potential impact of AI in Web 3.0 can be significant for various stakeholders, including users, businesses, and society as a whole [16].

Here's an analysis of the potential impact of AI in Web 3.0 on these stakeholders [16]:

Users: AI in Web 3.0 can significantly improve the user experience by enabling more personalized, intuitive, and efficient interactions between users and machines. AI can also improve the security and privacy of user data, enabling users to trust the systems they interact with. However, users may also face concerns about data privacy, bias, and transparency, and organizations must ensure that they are addressing these concerns to maintain user trust [16].

Businesses: AI in Web 3.0 can offer significant benefits for businesses, such as increased efficiency, productivity, and profitability. AI can also enable businesses to personalize their offerings, improving customer satisfaction and loyalty. However, businesses may also face challenges around data privacy and security, as well as concerns about bias and ethical implications of AI systems [16].

Society: AI in Web 3.0 has the potential to transform society by enabling more efficient and effective interactions between individuals and organizations. For example, AI can improve healthcare outcomes by enabling more accurate diagnoses and treatments, and can enable more efficient and sustainable transportation systems. However, society may also face challenges

related to data privacy, bias, and ethical implications of AI systems, and it is important that these challenges are addressed to ensure that the benefits of AI are realized for all members of society [16].

2.3.2. decentralized autonomous organization

It is usually encapsulated in a set of rules and procedures that regulate conduct of participants in a system. Moving to more decentralized forms of governance, ideally performed on-chain, requires modifying corporate governance processes to fit the idiosyncrasies of blockchains. In the DeFi and blockchain space, governance, decision-making and operations are typically performed through DAOs. The BG framework, defining the governance structure of a blockchain as a combination between six governance dimensions, and three governance layers [18].

Figure 3. DAO [17]

Figure 3. Shows DAO consist on some token holders and then aggregated to delegated component to create or vote on proposals.

DAOs could mitigate sybil attacks with Soulbound Tokens (SBTs) in several ways, by [19]:

- computing over a Soul’s constellation of SBTs to differentiate between unique Souls and probable bots, and denying any voting power to a Soul that appears to be a Sybil [19].
- conferring more voting power to Souls who hold more reputable SBTs—like work or educational credentials, licenses, or certifications [19].
- issuing specialized “proof-of-personhood” SBTs, which could help other DAOs bootstrap sybil resistance [19].
- checking for correlations between SBTs held by Souls who support a particular vote, and applying a lower vote weight to voters who are highly correlated [19].

2.3.3. Tokenized carbon credits

Tokenized carbon credits are central to Regenerative Finance (ReFi), a subset of Decentralized Finance (DeFi), named after a broader movement in regenerative capitalism which is primarily concerned with climate change mitigation through digital assets of various kinds. Tokenized carbon credits have been studied in relation to the energy industry, the transition into sustainable energy, and how to maximize the efficiency of current grids by allowing for peer-

to-peer energy trading.²⁵ There is also research regarding solutions for measurement, reporting, and verification (MRV),²⁶ and sustainable supply chains [5].

2.3.4. Programmable Carbon

We consider interoperability in terms of the applications that are built on carbon credits. Because interoperability manifests itself in part in how easy or difficult it is to build applications on top of these credits, the kinds of applications which build on tokenized carbon credits are a key component that could inform token interoperability standards. There are already a variety of applications that build directly on tokenized carbon credits or the data which backs credits. Let us review a number of them, and then discuss some key takeaways. The Climate Collective is a coalition of entrepreneurs, investors, non-profit organizations, and scientists, whose aim is to promote blockchains and cryptocurrencies (Web3 infrastructure) as a tool for climate action at scale [5].

Offsetting Services

A primary purpose of tokenized carbon credits is that they can be retired to offset emissions. Aside from the retirement functionality that all tokenized carbon credits given here offer, there are already some services built around offsetting emissions. For example, from the projects we have seen, Flowcarbon also offers automated offsetting for Web3 users and Nori offers automated offsetting for businesses [5].

Carbon-Backed Digital Assets

There is an emerging landscape of tokenized digital assets which are backed by carbon credits or related climate data. KlimaDAO, who works with Toucan, issues a carbon-backed currency called KLIMA. tokens are backed by at least one retired carbon credit from various sources, including BCT and MCO2 tokens. KLIMA can also be minted by the rules governing the treasury, which themselves are governed by the DAO. The goal of this project is to drive up demand for carbon credits, creating what they call a carbon economy in which the currency is carbon-backed, and the true cost of carbon is internalized into every transaction [1].

2.4. Reinforcement Learning

Reinforcement learning (RL) is a type of machine learning algorithm, where an intelligent agent, which is a computing system that perceives its environment to take actions autonomously in order to achieve cumulative rewards based on the knowledge gathered from the environment [12].

Figure 4. Representative diagram of intelligent agent [12].

Figure 4 shows a representative diagram of an intelligent agent. Here, reward could be optimizing performance or power consumption or thermal efficiency or combination of these together [12].

2.5. Cloud Computing

The general classification of distributed architecture and proposed architecture position is placed in different sections of cloud computing [3].

Cloud computing (cloud) is a computing model to enable ubiquitous, convenient, on-demand network access to a shared pool of configurable computing resources such as networks, servers, storage, applications, and services, which can be rapidly provisioned and released with minimal management effort or service provider interaction. The essential features of cloud computing include Broad network access, On-demand self-service, Rapid elasticity, Resource pooling, and Measured service. Cloud services can be provided to consumers in numerous ways, and one such service is Software as a service (also called SaaS), where the software and its related data are hosted in the cloud computing environment such that the software could be provided to numerous consumers [12].

2.6. IOT

smart cities are now able to implement a sequence of innovative ICT technologies such as cloud computing, IoT and other associated infrastructure to manage the physical flow of information across the city. Al-Fuqaha opined that internet of things (IoT) can be categorized into 3-layers with regards to architecture and function block which are IoT middleware, IoT service, IoT infrastructure while the data operation procedure in the present internet of things technologies consists of 4-phases which are collecting, analyzing, delivering and applying [14].

2.7. Society 5.0

The social issue in question concerns the need to minimize “carbon emissions/capita.” However, individual members of society wish to increase the third component “total activity/capita.” To balance these two interests, we must sufficiently reduce the first two of these components (“carbon emissions/total energy consumption” and “total energy consumption/total activity”) [5].

Figure 5. Analysis of carbon emissions [5].

Figure 5 shows the formula for calculating the KPI “carbon emissions/capita.” The formula shows two components of “carbon emissions/capita”: the first is “carbon emissions/total energy consumption” and the second is “total energy consumption/capita.” Total energy consumption represents the entirety of the energy used in Japan. Given that carbon emissions result from energy consumption, it makes sense to take the amount of total energy consumption into consideration when devising strategies for minimizing “carbon emissions/capita.” These two components under-score the fact that if we manage to reduce “carbon emissions/total energy consumption” enough, we will not necessarily need to reduce “total energy consumption/capita”; in other words, we will not need to be frugal with our energy consumption [5].

2.7.1. Institutional Work in Smart Cities: Interviews with Smart City Managers

Creating work type of institutional work

Second-order categories: Build the ICT architectures for data collection and exchange.

Build the necessary city infrastructure for data transfer such as fiber optic network, LoRa WAN, 5G, cloud infrastructure etc [13].

Standardize the data architecture formats and protocols to facilitate data exchange across different networks typologies [13].

Second-order categories: Foster citizen-centric services

Research and understand changing citizens' need and demands [13].

Enhance responsiveness of the city administration to the citizens' needs, points of views, critics and suggestions [13].

Rethink and redesign administrative processes and services from the citizen's perspective [13].

Maintaining work type of institutional work

Maintain existing IT infrastructure:

Make use of existing IT infrastructure and corresponding expertise [13].

Support individual departments and organizational units with the existing digital infrastructure in place [13].

Integrate old and new IT infrastructures:

Confirm the adequacy of the current technical infrastructure which is seen as still relevant by the administrative units [13].

Work towards harmonization and interoperability between new and existing IT systems and across organizational units [13].

2.8. Implemented works

2.8.1. Driverless cars

In recent times, there have been several studies on driverless cars and its adoption in the society. Driverless cars, or automated car generally refers to an automated car that operates on its own without human assistance [14].

2.8.2. Financial technology

It is predicted that the future smart cities will implement various financial technological approach. The use of blockchain technology has been noted in several literature as one of the financial technology approaches that can be used as means of transaction in a smart city [14].

2.8.3. e-voting system

A national e-voting system will be of great benefit to most developed and developing countries, because an e-voting system will strengthen the electoral process, curb electoral malpractices and improve the level of transparency in governance [14].

2.8.4. Automated pandemic detecting city

Pandemic wreaks havoc whenever it hits a country or any part of a country or even the world. It burdens lives, economies and the larger society [14].

2.8.5. Automated self-repairable smart city

Maintenance is a very significant aspect of infrastructure sustainability. The future smart city should have an automated self-repairable ability i.e ability to maintain itself automatically without any external assistance [14].

2.8.6. Online central government treasury app

Transparency in governance is one of the major problems of leadership in most developing nations, and adopting the use of technology will improve the level of transparency in governance, this system can also be referred to as a smart governance system [14].

2.8.7. Online education

Education plays a significant role in the development of a nation. It is envisaged that the future smart cities will implement a 100% online education and training, which will make education easily accessible and affordable [14].

2.8.8. Movable smart city

It is envisaged that the future smart cities should be movable from one point to another. As technologies continue to advance, new innovations and ideas are invented to improve the quality of life of humans [14].

3. Problem Statement

The planetary boundary framework, while providing a useful model for measuring change, is not fully accepted by all scientists. Some note that because the nine boundaries are all so deeply interconnected, it can be challenging to separate them out and evaluate each individually in a meaningful way. This is especially true for land system change, which underpins and

influences nearly every other boundary. Three of the PBs (climate change, stratospheric ozone depletion, and ocean acidification) remain essentially unchanged from the earlier analysis [2].

3.1. Social issues

One of the biggest concerns I have is there's a big group that's been funded by the World Bank that only use private blockchains. And it's basically just a way to do that. And I think the biggest risk is that not so much ReFi succeeding, but the ReFi public concept succeeding... As it becomes private, you fall into the trap of brokers or marketplaces having inventory, and then that inventory being dictated by them, and then you have this weird power play. And I think when you have it super-open and transparent, you open the floodgates for removing as many pain points as possible with those middlemen. And maybe that works privately, but less so [4].

3.2. Cost of Smart Contracts

Without paying for gas, the Ethereum smart contract cannot be carried out. In order to compare the fuel needed for the two methods of uploading the data, the fuel utilized to upload the original data was measured. The smallest unit of Ethereum money, the Gwei, is used to quantify fuel consumption. 109 Wei is referred to as Gwei. The price of contract migration execution is indicated in our proposed system. The price is specified in ether and includes the gas utilized. The amount of gas consumed multiplied by the price of gas equals one unit of ether. In this arrangement, the gas spent stands in for the continuous cost of computing. The value variations of ether in the account, the network has changed the price of gas [15].

Table 2. Analyze of the costs associated with data storage [15].

Execution Type	Gas Used	Cost in Ether
Contract Creation	2,027,188	0.04054376
Contract Migration Call	27,363	0.0054726
Initial Contract	225,237	0.0450474
Initial Migration Call	42,363	0.0084726

3.3. A New Problem with Pricing the Priceless

There are a host of other issues related to nonmonetary pricing models. One such issue is the divergence between production (e.g., GDP) and economic impact (user's satisfaction). In monetary economies, impact is generally tied to production, so it suffices to check the GDP. However, technological innovation has undermined this linkage, such that GDP can no longer be used as an indirect/alternative indicator of impact. Thus, we urgently require direct measures of economic impact. Some have suggested using willingness to pay (WTP) or willingness to accept (WTA) as direct measures of economic impact. WTP describes the maximum amount of money that consumers would be willing to pay for a free product. WTA describes the minimum amount of money that consumers would be willing to accept to abandon a free product. Both WTP and WTA are gaged through consumer surveys [5].

Some of these services are payable. It is not always clear when payable services will become free, but as Rifkin argues, the Collaborative Commons will only grow ever larger in the future.

This trend is not necessarily at odds with capitalism. The Collaborative Commons is, in fact, supported by capitalism and it develops in tandem with it. In the course of this process, fewer goods and services will be exchanged, leading to a smaller GDP, but that does not mean that wealth declines. The question then is what does wealth mean in the context of this process and what changes will occur in the values underpinning such wealth [5]?

3.3.1. Sharing as a New Value

The Collaborative Commons will expand the bounds of common value, such that many products will be commonly accessed without anyone privately owning them. This situation will decrease market transactions, GDP, and incomes, but wealth will remain high. The present capitalist society defines wealth as how much an individual privately owns. In the Collaborative Commons, wealth is measured by how much is shared. One can be rich without owning lots of things and without earning the money necessary to own lots of things [5].

3.4. The Advantages and Problems of Digital Platforms

The open communities that digital platforms will serve an indispensable market function in Society 5.0's trading. These platforms facilitate trade by indicating non-monetary information as well as monetary price. This information empowers buyers to make informed choices about what to purchase, and the culmination of these consumer choices will encourage businesses to develop more creative products and services to compete [5].

For example, the privatization of infrastructure. The government is pursuing a plan to entrust the management of infrastructure such as waterworks and roads to private operators as part of a structural reform and regulatory easing project intended to encourage creative innovation in the private sector. Traditionally, the whole infrastructure was maintained through cross-subsidization; profitable infrastructure propped up unprofitable infrastructure. However, if profitable infrastructure is in private hands, the survival of unprofitable infrastructure becomes doubtful. As public services become increasingly marketized, services with doubtful profitability may be shed. We need a system that distinguishes between those services that should emphasize profit and those that should prioritize the public good over profit. The second point is that we must address the information asymmetry in digital platforms. Austrian-born economist Friedrich Hayek saw markets as places for communicating information. Through market-determined pricing, participants' private information is shared on the market as public information, which allows the market to play a public role—that of balancing demand with supply. In so doing, the market stores public knowledge and becomes democratized [5].

However, digital platforms differ from Hayek's conception of the market in that the platform operator profits. There is considerable information asymmetry between the platform operator and the platform participants; the latter share their knowledge with the platform operator but not with each other. If the knowledge becomes a tool of the platform operator, then this nullifies the advantage of the participants possessing knowledge; consequently, the participants' services become commodified. This situation creates a profitability gap; platform operators achieve sustained profitability by gathering the knowledge and using it to make their operations more efficient, while the platform participants struggle to maintain profitability because their services are commodified. We are already witnessing these gaps growing at an alarming rate in digital platforms. If the platform participants have the option of switching to an alternative platform operator, they may find a way to avert the commodification of their services. However, if there is a strong network effect, this will create the winner-takes-all situation

described earlier, eliminating all but a few platform operators. This bottleneck will deprive the participants of choice [5].

4. Proposed Work

Our aim is converting data which is generated by IOT devices, feedback of users, feedback of current designed system, a smart contract or DAO of blockchain. there are some solutions and ideas that can be done.

4.1. Automation of process

Imagine that achieving this facility for citizens requires the construction of heated pavement systems that melt snow and ice away via resistive heating. The ability of future smart cities to self-maintain will improve their efficiency and integrity and further reduce the cost of maintenance labor. So, self-maintaining, in conjunction with smart contracts, will deduct taxes from citizens' accounts spontaneously.

Every smart contract will have externalities (carbon tokens, supply chain characteristics, and ESG attributes) embedded, priced, and made transparent per the customer's specific requirements.

There are some frameworks that are written in Solidity or Rust. They cover some features of the smart contract standard. It is a tree of characteristics and attributes that must propose new solution to fit the idiosyncrasies of business. Canonical attributes can run when predetermined conditions are met. Existing frameworks only tackle conditions in a one-level process. When the overload is met, conflict and abuse of functions will expose. It is not about code smells; it is about structure or pattern and the priority of subtasks for passing a function with a lot of parameters. Radically, based on a complex model of business, we can use a programming language to convert an array of BITS from all of their characteristics and attributes to feed a smart contract. In addition, make encryption the input and output data depend on your decision.

4.2. All-encompassing events

People can give feedback to many posts and stories on social media, while we do not have any kind of physical or tangible attention when encountering natural events around us. We can detect the location of a user, but we cannot detect where people are present. So, there is a solution to eliminate any kind of middle instrument or technologies like insisting on using satellites for better longitude and latitude, or maybe insisting on creating a new expensive electronic device. The only thing that we need is to install a cheap embedded device, like a tiny device on the bus. After that, the user's application can receive the characteristics of the specified bus. For example, users will take action on their position in the bus, which means they can make new data with feedback via the application to determine if they are satisfied with their chair or not. Eventually, citizens give like or dislike to the physical world.

4.3. Multiple ownerships

Re-fungibility is an important step towards building real-life models of ownership rights. Often, a special option may be owned by some people in various proportions. Examples of

such shared ownership are abundant: timeshares, co-ownership of art, fractional car ownership, land, real-estate, etc. For that purpose, the re-fungible token can be minted and then partially transferred to different owners. Eventually, fictionalizing assets leads to non-unique game resources, rating points in applications with social networking capabilities, voting tokens, and other new capabilities.

4.4. Sovereign and governance

4.4.1. Corporate governance vs Decentralized Autonomous

Create a new model of on-chain governance. DAO governance today looks a lot like off-chain corporate governance. Using only a whitelisted strategy is not enough, and implementing a credit strategy would be helpful with staking. The proposed approach is using a hybrid governance model, although the next generation of DAOs will be SBTs for mitigating Sybil attacks.

4.4.2. Voting Governance Model

Governance token holders can delegate their tokens to others (who do not even need to hold GT) to vote. The proposed platform will have the capability to propose (submit proposed name 21SC Improvement Proposals, or CIPs) and vote.

Participants must lock up their 21SC (21SC DAO's governance token would be called a vote escrowed 21SC/veSC) by transferring them from their private wallets (in Polkadot ecosystem it has known a controller account) to the voting contract (from where they can be later withdrawn).

21SC holders can lock their tokens so they can obtain veSC in order to gain voting and proposal-making powers. There is a voting power minimum, but a user must have veSC to create a proposal. Imagine the protocol uses a multi-DAO structure consisting of independent sub-DAOs that would combine form the protocol governance. 21SC holders can vote for changes, but decisions are sent, as a delegated transaction to the Multisig, which either executes or vetoes the transaction.

4.4.3. Community token governance models

There are some parties that can effectively control governance through what is called the Council Governance Model. Governance token holders' approval only comes from the ESG Council, which consists of seven annually elected individuals that review the proposals. The model would be in spite of plutocracy, which is the counterargument that large token holders have the largest interest in making decisions as a kind of sovereign.

4.5. Value-driven consumption

Adopting a value-driven approach to consumption can be beneficial across various sectors, including supply chain management, marketing initiatives such as customer acquisition and advertising, and in shaping financial strategies and guidance.

For such an approach to be effective, it necessitates foundational elements like DAOs, robust information-gathering systems for comprehensive data, continuous monitoring mechanisms, and financial programs that are responsive to seasonal or annual trends, along with sufficient liquidity. The hallmarks of value-driven consumption include the ability to gauge customer

satisfaction, assess quality metrics, maintain a compliant treasury, segment consumer spending, and offer promotions and rewards that emphasize quality.

In the context of energy trading platforms, especially those aiming for Net-Zero carbon emissions, this approach becomes increasingly relevant. Addressing the energy shortage involves creating liquidity pools, supported by derivative or futures contracts, to ensure sustainable liquidity. Within these liquidity pools, X Market Maker algorithms will govern consumption based on supply and demand dynamics. Ultimately, managing consumption in this way fosters a value-oriented ecosystem that benefits both retailers and Terms of Carriage (TOCs).

4.6. Proposed Architecture

Figure 6. 21SmartCity Framework

Figure 6 shows the proposed framework that consist of five layers. Layer 2 requires tests. If implementing Layer 2 would have significant challenges, we are set to use IPFS (decentralized storage) with mitigating performance inevitably. Regard to “Sensors Data Retrieving” would be every kind of device, e.g., a device for detecting the extinguished cigarettes of a user in a social space. Eventually, proposed work able to detect and manage users’ rewards based on token engineer and then convert it to carbon credit with regard to the next figure.

Figure 7. Carbon market [2]

Figure 7 shows credits and capital flows on the voluntary carbon market.

5. Future prospects and research directions

Developing interoperability standards: As AI systems become more prevalent in Web 3.0, it is important to develop interoperability standards that enable different systems and applications to exchange data seamlessly [16].

Further research is needed to develop and implement these standards. Investigating new business models: The increased efficiency and personalization enabled by AI in Web 3.0 are likely to lead to the emergence of new business models and opportunities. Further research is needed to investigate these new business models and their implications for the economy [16].

Studying the integration with other emerging technologies: The integration of AI in Web 3.0 with other emerging technologies, such as blockchain and the Internet of Things (IoT), is likely to enable new use cases and applications. Further research is needed to study the integration of AI with these technologies and their implications for Web 3.0 [16].

Based on the 21SC framework, there is a weakness in the section of Data or Storage layer. Writing and reading of decentralized storages have costs, especially time, while in the scope of IOT and smart cities we expect having real-time data exchange.

However, it appears that some of the greatest challenges facing ReFi are in how successfully it manages to avoid reproducing structural inequalities that have plagued climate action and conservation work more broadly. Reconfiguring market-based approaches to climate governance, as ReFi and Smart City are attempting, requires significant structural change, which may have other adverse consequences.

6. Conclusion

In conclusion, the proposed framework, with its five-layer structure, represents a significant stride towards harnessing the power of Web 3.0 for sustainable urban development. The challenges of implementing Layer 2 and the potential use of IPFS for decentralized storage underscore the need for rigorous testing and performance optimization. The innovative approach to "Sensors Data Retrieving" through devices like extinguished cigarette detectors in social spaces exemplifies the practical application of this technology in monitoring environmental impact and rewarding positive user behavior.

Depiction of the voluntary carbon market, particularly within the Klima DAO, illustrates the tangible flow of credits and capital that could drive the economy towards more eco-conscious decisions. The integration of AI, as emphasized, is pivotal for the seamless interoperability of diverse systems, fostering the emergence of new business models that capitalize on the efficiency and personalization afforded by Web 3.0 technologies. However, the journey ahead is not without its obstacles. The research highlights the imperative of developing interoperability standards and exploring the symbiosis of ReFi with blockchain and IoT.

The 21SC framework proposed a replacement of Storage layer, where the latency in decentralized storage systems poses a challenge to the real-time data exchange essential for IoT and smart cities. Addressing these concerns will be crucial for realizing the full potential of a value-based, efficient, and equitable Web 3.0 ecosystem. Six proposed solution serves as a clarion call for continued research and innovation in the field, urging stakeholders to navigate the complexities of this digital transformation with foresight and responsibility. The convergence of AI, blockchain, ReFi, and smart city technologies holds the promise of a more sustainable and equitable future, but it is incumbent upon us to ensure that this promise is fulfilled without exacerbating existing disparities.

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Declaration of competing interest

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